

Dipolar Cycloaddition of Chloroketene to *o*-Nitrocinnamalanilines

M. R. MANRAO*, ANIL KUMAR and P. S. KALSI

Department of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

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Dipolar cycloaddition of chloroketene, prepared *in situ* from monochloroacetyl chloride and triethylamine to *o*-nitrocinnamalanilines yields δ -lactams in excellent yields. The structures of these compounds are supported by elemental analyses and spectral studies. Substitution by electron-withdrawing nitro group in the *C*-phenyl ring seems to retard the reaction.

CHLOROKETENES¹ add to imines to give β -lactams²⁻⁵. When the imine function is a part of a conjugated system both 1,2- and 1,4-cycloadducts are possible. However, cinnamalanilines have been reported to undergo 1,4-cycloaddition only to give δ -lactams⁴. In continuation of our work⁶⁻⁸ on the effect of nitro substituent on the reactions of conjugated Schiff bases, this paper describes the reaction of monochloroketene with *o*-nitrocinnamalanilines.

o-Nitrocinnamalanilines (3) were prepared by condensing *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde with aniline and substituted anilines⁹. The dropwise addition of monochloroacetyl chloride (1) to the benzene solution of *o*-nitrocinnamalaniline and triethylamine at room temperature yielded a crystalline product. This product was identified as δ -lactam (4) on the basis of elemental analyses and ir studies. The band at 1 690 cm⁻¹ and not at ~1 780 cm⁻¹ in the infrared spectrum of the adduct was used to identify δ -lactam system. δ -Lactams synthesised from various *o*-nitrocinnamalanilines by the addition monochloroacetyl chloride in the presence of triethylamine are recorded in Table 1.

(4)

The presence of electron-withdrawing nitro group in the *C*-phenyl nucleus seems to lower the

reactivity of these Schiff bases (3) since out of a total nine such Schiff bases adducts were successfully obtained only in five cases, and in these cases too on the whole the yields of the adducts were comparatively lower than the corresponding adducts obtained from cinnamalanilines. On the other hand, presence of electron-withdrawing substituents in the *N*-phenyl ring of the Schiff bases seems to increase their reactivity as indicated by comparatively higher yields in case of *o*-nitrocinnamal-*p*-chloroaniline and *o*-nitrocinnamal-*p*-bromoaniline.

It was also observed that if the reaction was carried out in the absence of triethylamine 1:1*N*-acylated adducts were obtained in quantitative yields which changed into δ -lactam on refluxing in benzene solution. The *N*-acylated adducts also yielded δ -lactams on addition of triethylamine, but the yields were poor (20-30%) and a considerable amount of tars was obtained. Thus, it is postulated that in the presence of triethylamine the elimination process was probably favoured over the acylation of the Schiff base by acid chloride.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF δ -LACTAMS

Compd. no.	Substituent in <i>N</i> -phenyl nucleus	M.p.* °C	Yield %	Molecular formula**
4a	H	165	60	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ NO ₂ Cl
4b	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃	195	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ NO ₂ Cl
4c	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	145	58	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂ Cl
4d	<i>p</i> -Cl	167	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ NO ₂ Cl ₂
4e	<i>p</i> -Br	180	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ NO ₂ ClBr

* All the melting points are uncorrected.

** All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses

Experimental

The following general procedure was followed for the synthesis of δ -lactams. *o*-Nitrocinnamalaniline (0.01 mol) was dissolved in benzene (25 ml) and to it added triethylamine (0.02 mol). To the

above mixture was added monochloroacetyl chloride (0.02 mol) taken in benzene (25 ml) slowly and with constant stirring at room temperature. After the addition of chloroacetyl chloride was complete, the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 3-4 h. Removal of solvent under vacuum yielded a crude product which was recrystallised from ethanol to get pure crystals of δ -lactam (60%), m.p. 165°.

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